

AR6 WGI Chapter Scientists Feedback Survey Report

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Written by Connors, S., Masson-Delmotte, V., and Pirani, A.

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Summary

Chapter Scientists (CS) play essential roles in the IPCC report drafting process. The CS role is usually undertaken by an early career scientist who supports a specific chapter, assisting on more technical tasks such as document and citation management and figure development. The Working Group I Technical Support Unit (WGI TSU) undertook a short feedback survey to gather the views and experiences from the WGI AR6 CSs. The survey responses show that the CS role is a unique opportunity for early career scientists to gain experience and knowledge of the IPCC process and of the latest climate change research, however the workload is often overburdened with junior scientists taking on more responsibilities than previously expected and sometimes with resulting ethics of authorship / acknowledgement issues in the author team. In this report, the WGI TSU and Bureau provides some recommendations for future IPCC cycles to improve the CS role within the Working Group I assessment process, including updated Terms of References on the role and its expectations. A unified approach to this role across the Working Groups is recommended to the IPCC.

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Introduction to the Chapter Scientist role

Chapter Scientists (CS) are usually early career scientists that support a chapter’s development during the IPCC report writing process. They aid in the more technical and logistical tasks, such as managing the chapter reference database, technical editing of the chapter drafts, or supporting figure development. The names of chapter scientists are listed on the front page of chapters but, as for Contributing Authors and Review Editors, they are not included in chapter citations that includes only the Coordinating Lead Authors and Lead Authors.

This report focuses solely on the AR6 WGI practices and experiences of the CS role, but the CS role has been present in [AR5](#), as well as the AR6, across all three Working Groups (WGs). There is no standardised approach to CS recruitment or to their Terms of Reference across the three WGs. More often, as was the case in the WGI AR6, CSs are recruited by chapter Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs), either with a specific working contract or as part of an already contracted postdoc, PhD or masters position. The WGI TSU covered funding to support the travel of Chapter Scientists when needed.

Terms of reference (TOR) for the CS role were given to CLAs at the beginning of the assessment process to aid their recruitment efforts (See Annex I). For WGI AR6, CLAs appointed chapter scientists from their own funding sources.

The WGI AR6 assessment lists 29 CSs across its 13 chapters. On average, each chapter was supported by 2 CS, however the maximum number of CSs reached per chapter was 5 (Chapter 9) and the minimum was 1 (Chapters 5, 6, 10). All 29 CSs were based at the same institution as one of the CLAs but only 6 of the 29 CS (21%) were based in a developing country institution. **Figure 1 Panel A** shows the regional distribution of all 29 CS as defined by the WMO regions. 17 CS (59%) were based in Europe, 6 (21%) within North America, Central America and the Caribbean, 3 (10%) in Asia, and only 1 CS (3%) was based in Africa, South America, and the South West Pacific region, respectively¹. There was no standardized start date for CS across the chapters and as such CS started throughout the WGI AR6 drafting process. **Figure 1 Panel B** shows the number of CS attending their first WGI AR6 meeting along the drafting process. No CS had started by the first Lead Author Meeting (LAM1) in June 2018 but 10 joined by LAM2 (January 2019) and another 10 by LAM3 (August 2019). A further 7 joined by the virtual ‘pre-LAM4 activities’ (June-September 2020) sessions and 2 final CS joined by the virtual LAM4 (January 2021). CS end dates were also not standardized. Many CS continued to work during the lead up to the WGI approval of the Summary for Policymakers (SPM) and contributed to data and code archival tasks after the approval however end dates were not well documented by the WGI TSU and no overview can be provided.

¹ 99% due to rounding.

Figure 1: Statistical of the WGI AR6 Chapter scientists. A) The geographical regions of the host country in which the CS are based. Regions are based on the WMO regional classification² what the IPCC follows. B) Approximate start dates of the CS throughout the WGI AR6 process. LAM = Lead author meeting. The pre-LAM4 was a series of virtual events that concluded in September 2020. N=29

The survey

After the WGI report was released, CSs were sent a short feedback survey, comprising 15 questions to gather an understanding of their experiences and recommendations for future IPCC cycles. The survey was sent for responses between 14 to 28 March 2022, roughly 9 months after the Summary for Policymakers was approved and as the production of the report’s chapters was coming to an end. The survey was intentionally designed to be anonymous to encourage as honest feedback as possible. It therefore did not contain any questions asking for personal data, for example name, nationality etc., nor did it ask in which chapter they were based. The survey questions covered topics such as the tasks CSs were involved with, how demanding were these tasks, whether they worked beyond the stated terms of reference among others. A copy of the survey questions can be found in Annex II.

² <https://community.wmo.int/governance/regional-association>

Survey analysis

Of the 29 CSs, 15 (52%) responded to the survey. This is a small sample size and as such it may not be appropriate to extrapolate these results to represent the range of views across all CSs, however the responses still offer insight into what just over half of the WGI CSs experienced.

Contract type

To the question ‘What type of contract was your chapter scientist role?’, nine (60%) responded that they were working part time while undergoing a full time postdoctoral research contract. Other contract / employment types included part time while studying for a PhD or masters (7%), part time as part of a full time employment position (14%), part time self-employed (7%). One person responded that they worked as part of a full time employed role as a senior scientist. Only one person responded that they were contracted as a full time CS. The survey did not ask how workload changed across the WGI timeline, but it can be noted that there were often periods of more intense workload, for example leading up to chapter draft submission deadlines, compared to other periods where workload was more balanced, of example during reviews of the drafts. This imbalanced distribution of work would have affected CS who were not on full time contract.

Tasks, responsibilities and workload

Terms of Reference

CSs were asked which roles listed in the original TOR were they involved with and to list other roles, if any, they performed outside of these TORs. Of the listed TORs, the most widespread task conducted was managing content on the Document Management System (14 responses, 93%), followed by assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions (11 responses, 73%).

There is a diversity of roles for a CS, as it shows not all CSs took part in all roles, for example, under half of the respondents mentioned that they undertook monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters or organising of chapter teleconferences.

Initial terms of reference with the number of associated responses

n=15 for all options

- Managing content on the Document Management system (14 responses, 93%)
- Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions (11 responses, 73%)
- Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley (10 responses, 67%)
- Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables (10 responses, 67%)
- Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter) (10 responses, 67%)
- Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting (10 responses, 67%)
- Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times (10 responses, 67%)
- Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and glossary (10 responses, 67%)
- Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report (8 responses, 53%)
- Assisting with traceability checking (8 responses, 53%)

- Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters (7 responses, 47%)
- Organisation of chapter teleconferences (7 responses, 47%)

These initial TORs were drafted at the beginning of the WGI report drafting process. Most tasks listed were carried out by half of the responses and so generally captured what was needed from CSs. The survey shows that CS also undertook several other additional tasks that were not listed in the TORs. These included tasks that are normally expected of chapter authors like replying to review comments, helping to draft FAQs, taking part in the chapter assessment. If CS make these contributions, they need to be recognised as Contributing Authors. For example, one specific response to this question was being the “main responsible author for one topic and heavily involved in writing one subchapter [section]”, which is a major concern since this is the role expected of a LA.

CS also completed a wider range of technical tasks including writing code to produce figures and analysis, and data documentation for archival. The development of figures, supporting metadata and the data archival tasks were projects that evolved during the drafting process in particular related to a new effort undertaken by WGI to the implementation of the FAIR principles. This was expected to be a chapter-wide responsibility, but all chapters allocated a CS as the point of contact for this task (only two chapters listed an additional author as another point of contact. This implies that much of the coordination work of this task fell on their shoulders.

Contributing Authors

What is not considered part of the CS remit is to take part in the chapter assessment. The published WGI AR6 report shows that 20 out of the 29 CS became CAs on their chapters (69%). All chapter scientists and CAs are also listed on their chapter’s Supplementary Material (additional, online only documents that support the chapter assessment). One CS is listed as the coordinator of one of the Chapter’s Supplementary Material. 13 CS (45%) are listed as CAs to either other chapters (8, 28%) or to report Annexes (8, 28%). Six CSs (21%) are listed purely as a CS role. On average, a CS is listed as a contributing author to two documents (chapters, supplementary materials or annexes). The highest number of documents to which a CS contributed was six (four chapters, one annex and the coordinator of the chapter supplementary material).

If CS make contributions to the substance of the chapter (e.g., responding to review comments, producing figures, drafting parts of text), then they should be recognised as a Contributing Author (CA) to that chapter. The survey asked for those who contributed to the chapter assessment whether they were recognised as CAs for this additional commitment. Of the 10 that responded, all said that they had been accredited as a CA. On a related topic of having recognition for their contributions, it should be noted that in another survey question response, one participant mentioned that they helped to draft an Annex but was not listed as a CS for that document. This raises the important issues of ethics of authorship (see Recommendations section).

Workload of tasks

CSs were asked how time consuming their main tasks were relative to each other. For this question, tasks that were not listed in the initial TOR but were known responsibilities often carried out by CS were included, such as code & data archival, data tables, and storing metadata on figure manager. **Figure 2** shows the relative workload distributions of the tasks. Tasks most often stated as ‘very time consuming’ were code & data archival, compiling data tables, tasks related to figures and handling excel files to deal with review comments. The least time consuming task was reported to be using Mendeley to handle chapter references, followed by managing the document manager system and the word template.

Figure 2: Time-consuming tasks with respect to the Chapter Scientist role overall as a percentage. n=15 for all options. Colour-coding refers to the relative amount of time spent on each task, in decreasing demand: **Very time consuming**, **Pretty time consuming**, **A bit time consuming**, **Minimal/not time consuming**, **I don't know**, **Not Applicable**.

Best and worst aspects of the role

CSs were asked to explain the 'best' and 'worst' parts of doing the role. These questions were open ended text box questions. 13 and 14 responses were collected for the 'best' and 'worst' questions, respectively.

Word clouds showing the most common words that occurred in these responses are found in **Figure 3**. The most common words for the 'best' answers were 'IPCC' (6 times), followed by 'learned' and 'process' (5 times each) reflecting the knowledge learnt from the experience and being part of the IPCC process. The most common words for the 'worst' answers were 'work' (13 times), 'chapter' (9 times), 'authors' (5 times) and 'time' (5 times) reflecting the workload in relation to the authors' and also their interaction with the authors..

Figure 3: Word cloud from respondents' answers on the 'best' (a) and 'worst' (b) parts of the CS role. Text size reflects the number of times the word was used in the responses. The max number of occurrences was 6 and 13 for (a) and (b), respectively, whereas the minimum number of occurrences was 3 for both word clouds.

Responses to the best parts of being a CS included networking and building more contacts, learning about new science, and being able to contribute to the IPCC process, for example:

- “Knowledge gained. I learned so much about the IPCC process. I also expanded my knowledge of the subject matter and found listening to the authors discuss the assessment and assignment of confidence to be really helpful.”
- “Networking opportunities, a sort of pride in being involved with the IPCC and contributing to something important”
- “Access to the latest literature, participating in the IPCC process. Building science contacts.”
- “Aside from getting one's name in the Chapter (!), the best part is getting to work with the world's leading climate scientists in the world's most important climate assessment publication.”
- “Very interesting and exciting experience, also a very fulfilling and useful thing to work on! Made some good connections with more senior scientists and had some opportunities to be a coauthor on some papers directly related to the IPCC work.”

The worst part of being a CS is also clearly shown in the survey responses: the workload and the lack of perceived recognition or credit for doing the work. A couple of the responses mentioned specific tasks such as managing the references in Mendeley or creating the data tables but the main focus of the responses here was on workload and stress. For example:

- “No recognition and enormous workload under low guidance. Since starting in June 2020 until the end, I was working crazy hours (10am-10pm), from January to March even working 12-14 hours/day over the weekends without doing anything outside the chapter preparation, and at the end not being included into [the] citation. At the same time, it was hard to understand certain points since I joined so late in the process, and it was incredibly hard to find some guidelines or information.”
- “The type of work I did for the report and the amount of effort I put into it only barely resembled the Terms of Reference for a chapter scientist. There were many long days and nights trying to stay caught up that it took a severe toll on my physical and mental health.”

- “The amount of time and energy consumed. High stress levels for long periods of time and lack of proper recognition. The work comes on top of a research position which suffered in a part of our career where building your CV is essential. Many CSs are also young adults with small kids. Balancing IPCC, day job and family was nearly impossible. Years of effort with little to show for it. Put as much, if not more, time and effort into this as lead authors, but all we get in return is our name printed on the front page in a role that reads like assistant.”

Some responses also talked about a lack of respect between them as CS and some of the chapter authors. A few responses touch on the difficulty of interacting with more ‘senior’ scientists, requesting them for information for tasks such as figure metadata documentation.

- “The last point was an extremely not caring attitude of some figure developers with regards to metadata and datasets submission.”
- “Sometimes being treated like a student rather than a colleague”
- “Non-leading CLAs”
- “Sometimes I was not completely sure about how far I could go in organizing the work in my chapter. Since I’m a junior scientist from a minority group I needed CLA’s encouragement to keep track of the chapter’s work (insisting by email and during the LAM).”
- “The stress, the effect it had on my health and relationships, the lack of recognition, feeling that many tasks were pointless and unmotivating, being castigated by LAs of other chapters.”

One comment reflects a misunderstanding or miscommunication, possibly with their chapter CLAs, with respect to being included in the chapter citation: “We were promised that we would be cited, and therefore have many citation numbers associated with us”. Chapter citations only include the CLAs and LAs as they are selected through an open and transparent process including agreement from the IPCC Panel and who have responsibility for the scientific quality of the chapter. Contributing Authors and Chapter Scientists are not listed in the citation. While the Terms of Reference indicate clearly, “The contribution of Chapter Scientists is acknowledged and their names are listed as Chapter Scientists on the first page of the corresponding report chapter”, this may be misunderstood and this ambiguity could be avoided by stating more explicitly that chapter scientists are not included in chapter citations.

Recommending the CS role to others

There was a split in the answers to the survey question How likely are you to recommend this role to others in the future? Of the 15 responses, nine (60%) stated that they were either likely or very likely to recommend the role. Five of the responses (33%) said they were either unlikely or very unlikely to recommend the role. There was one response (7%) that stated they were neither likely nor unlikely and one response (7%) that said they didn’t know (**Figure 4**).

When comparing these responses to a question that asked whether CS worked beyond the original Terms of Reference (TOR), there were five responses who clearly stated they did more than the TOR. Of these five, four of them stated they were either unlikely or very unlikely to recommend the role (one said they were very likely). Of the 10 responses who said they worked within the TOR or left the question blank, seven stated that they were either likely or very likely to recommend the role (one said I don’t know, one stated neither likely nor unlikely). Although this is a very small sample size, it could be said that CS who had a more restricted and contained workload that was consistent with the TORs are more likely to recommend the role to others.

Figure 4: Survey responses to the question How likely are you to recommend this role to others in the future? n=15

Suggestions from the CSs on how to improve the role in the future

The survey asked CSs for recommendations for improving both the role in general, as well as the individual tasks going forwards. To improve the role in general, or to reduce the negative experiences, the responses from the survey suggested:

- The CS role be more clearly defined at the start of the process (what is expected and what is not expected)
- Have more than one CS per chapter to share the workload
- Ensure CSs are all early career scientists
- Include CS in the chapter citation
- Provide training to all authors on the role of the CS
- Organise the process, timeline and deliverables for tasks earlier and more clearly

The role of the TSU is fundamental to supporting CSs. Overall, CSs appreciated the TSU guidance resources and the CS meetings held at lead author meetings. 14 out of 15 responses said that the tools, guidance, training were between somewhat and extremely helpful (one response said not helpful) however comments stated that further support would have been appreciated, particularly for CSs that joined later on in the process. Another comment stated that “more regular meetings (virtual or otherwise) would help with cohesion and collegiality, and identify any problems early in the process”. The TSU could have supported the CS as a group more to help them learn from each other, as stated by another comment “A close communication among CSs would be very helpful to know how each team works, as well as how we can adjust our working routines and make it more efficient.”

Suggestions from CSs in the survey for improving the workload and efficiency of specific tasks are summarised below.

Word template

- Style guidance that includes code to automatically edit issues of consistency
- Enable hyperlinks for callouts and referencing
- More guidance on appropriate place names (e.g, in regions of political sensitivity)

Comment spreadsheets

- Provide macros and code for compiling spreadsheets and checking comment responses
- Provide an online system to have centralised comment responses.

Figure development including metadata

- Have Figure Manager available at the beginning of the process along with clear guidance
- Be more selective on what metadata is needed, if possible
- Allow for coding scripts to be uploadable to the document manager system

Data tables, code and data archival

- Clearer instructions available at the beginning of the process
- Provide examples of code
- Further training to authors on requirements and principles to avoid an over-reliance on CSs
- Avoid duplicating the information on different archives (GitHub, DMS, figures and data manager)
- Note that one comment suggested to drop data tables in AR7

Feedback and recommendations from CLAs

After doing an initial analysis of the CS survey responses, the TSU sent 9 follow up questions to all Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs), asking them to provide details on the CS role. The questions asked can be seen in Annex III. The TSU received 22 responses, representing 12 of the 13 chapters.

When asked how their CS were recruited, 80% of the responses indicated that either current or former students/colleagues were hired who worked at the same institution of a CLA. Only 16% of responses stated that they formally announced/advertised for positions. One responses stated that a CS was recruited who was a post-doc based at an LA institution.

Most CS were recruited to work part-time while either researching (46%) or studying (11%). 25% were hired as full-time positions. Other responses included working part-time while being retired, or working flexibly so was only full time for specific parts of the process due to other commitments.

Funding for CS positions was wide ranging, with responses including:

- Being fully covered by existing grants
- Being topped-up with existing grants
- Through additionally sourced funds from ministries / other funding agencies
- Through overhead allocations of other grant types.
- Half-paid, half voluntary.
- Not funded.

The majority of responses (65%) said that it is best to have CS physically located at the institution of one of the CLAs although a couple of comments stated this depends on the type of work, for example, if the work is specialized, like working with sea level projections, then being placed with a CLA would work well, but working on references etc. could be done anywhere in the world.

When asked if the IPCC should develop a mechanism or framework to involve a chapter scientist from a developing country for each report chapter, 55% answered Yes, 23% answered No and 23% answered I don't know³. Some responses added comments that this would be good for capacity building. Several stated the CS positions should be at the institution of a CLA. One comment stated the position could be funded to be at the institution of the developing country CLA.

Several CLAs took the opportunity to provide further feedback in the final open ended question. Feedback and suggestions included allowing CSs to be further recognized for their contributions and calling for the IPCC to do more to support what is seen to be a 'necessary' role. For example:

- "The Chapter Scientist role is vital to the success and the quality of the final chapter result. Their ability to produce graphics, organise references and other material, and to liaise with the TS is vital as the LAs are probably too busy to spend significant time on these tasks."
- "Their contribution should be recognized even more visibly than it is today. Being included in the citation seems correct and natural. Many work much harder than the LAs..."
- "Promote to CA or even LA if [they] do good job."
- "Let us try hard to have more of that support. I cannot imagine being a CLA without CS."
- "Significant country-to-country and institution to institution variance in offered support for CS role is hugely problematic. We only had a CS from late in process and only because I was able to use my own funds - no support from institution or government. There should be a reasonable expectation stated to at least governments from Global North that any CLA should have a CS. TSU, Bureau and secretariat should actively support CLAs in getting a CS in such cases. There is presently no active attempt made, at least systematically, to assure this resource across all chapters with CLAs left somewhat to fend for themselves on the issue."
- "Comparing AR6 with previous reports, the need to archive all the code and data to produce all the figures introduced a lot of extra work compared to previous reports. This also meant most figures had to be made by the chapter scientists themselves, with assistance from LAs, CAs. This was 80-90% of the work of our chapter scientists. This was a big difference compared to AR4, AR5. Technical editing, references etc were only a relatively small amount of work for the chapter scientists."
- "I think we shouldn't underestimate the importance of these roles. 5 chapter scientists might sound excessive but we would have struggled without each of them. I am immensely grateful to all of them. I wonder if chapter scientists could be paid positions as part of the TSU that early career scientists apply for."

WGI Bureau and TSU recommendations

Chapter Scientists contribute an essential role in the IPCC report drafting process. In a time of ever increasing literature and the need for data transparency and documentation, the need for technical support for author teams increases. This needs attention by the IPCC, through the Bureau, careful management by CLAs and support by the TSU as it can otherwise lead to an unsustainable burden on CSs.

³ 101% due to rounding.

The responses to this survey provide unique insights into the experiences of the WGI AR6 CS and gives the WGI Bureau/TSU information to make recommendations for future IPCC cycles, as well as suggest updates to the Terms of Reference to better define the role.

Recommendations

- To the greatest extent possible, the TSU should provide all guidance and timelines for the report preparation along with required deliverables at the start of the process. Information is needed for CS to be able to plan ahead tasks to avoid a pile up against key deadlines and prepare for times when there is a peak work load. Recognising that some changes to the timeline may sometimes be inevitable, for example, COVID-19 caused delays and rescheduling of the timeline of AR6.
- Terms of reference (TORs) should be given to chapter CLAs and LAs with an accompanying guidance document that explains the role of the CS, its boundaries and some lessons learned from the AR6 experiences.
 - If the work requested of a CS goes beyond the TORs, this should be agreed to with the CLAs. CS can also consult a Bureau member or TSU if they have concerns that their work is over-stepping the TORs to ensure that their workload remains manageable.
- Collectively, efforts should be made to hire CS early in the process (by LAM2) to allow for better integration into the chapter teams. If CS are hired later then the TSU should provide support to familiarize them with the process and expectations more efficiently.
- CLAs should provide the TSU with information on the arrangements they have made for the CS working with them so that there is a clear, shared understanding of the time availability and tasks expected of the CS.
- TSU should provide regular meeting and training opportunities for the CSs as a group throughout the process so that a stronger network is build amongst the CS, also with the TSU. This can include regular opportunities to collect feedback and status checks on CSs to ensure workload is kept to an appropriate level. A TSU member should be identified as the liaison / point of contact for CS with whom they can consult and request support and guidance.
- Recognising the essential role the CSs play, the IPCC should establish a fund to support this role in AR7 and make sure the role can be consistently applied across all three WGs. The IPCC should consider funding the equivalent of *at least* one full-time position per chapter of each Working Group Report. It is recommended that these funds be flexibly applied (i.e. full time or part-time) to support individual situations. These funds can be used to allow CLAs to recruit CS(s) with the necessary skills to complete the TORs.
- The implementation of FAIR principles as part of the IPCC assessment in terms of code and data management, documentation, provision of access and curation needs to be part of the author role when producing figurers, instead of a reliance on CS. To support this. It would be an asset if CS had data science and management expertise, in addition to the TSU team including this expertise.
- Bureau and TSU should brief CLAs at the start of the process of the different authorship roles for the report in the context of the Chapter Scientist role and the ethics of authorship guidance provided to authors.
 - Chapter scientist ToRs do not include authorship of the chapter. If Chapter Scientists make substantive contributions to the report based on their area of expertise, e.g. responding to review comments, drafting text, developing figures, they must be included in the chapter list of Contributing Authors (CAs).

- Contributions that go beyond a CA role, e.g. being heavily involved in a chapter subsection, providing missing expertise in the chapter team, thus fulfilling a LA role, this needs to be flagged to the Bureau by CLAs in advance to be appropriately managed, including consideration of whether the CS should be confirmed as a LA. Selection as a LA should be undertaken by the Bureau, in the context of expertise, geographical and gender balance, before a substantial contribution is made.

Updated Terms of Reference

The experience of CS during the AR6 WGI experience included working with the TSU on the implementation of FAIR data principles. These tasks have been added as an update to the TORs:

- Managing content on the Document Management system
- Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions
- Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley
- Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables
- [Overseeing the provision of metadata of chapter figures to Figure Manager](#)
- [Supporting authors to compile figure data tables](#)
- [Preparation of data and code for publication, supporting authors where relevant](#)
- Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)
- Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting
- Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times
- Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and glossary
- Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report
- Assisting with traceability checking
- Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters
- Organisation of chapter teleconferences

Improving the CS role more widely in the IPCC

Reflecting on the feedback from both CS and CLAs in these surveys, it is clear that the CS role is a necessary role that fundamentally supports the development of each chapter in IPCC reports. The CS role exists in all WGs with some common approaches but also some strikingly different ones, including how CS are recruited and paid. Issues to address may include:

- CLA support needs
- Terms of reference
- Funding and remuneration
- Recognition of the CS role in the preparation of IPCC reports
- Regional representation
- Capacity building in the IPCC process

Care is recommended not to confuse the capacity building aspect with the need for CLA support in general. A dedicated discussion is needed across the IPCC to establish a common framework and/or a more systematic mechanism to support these roles as core parts of the IPCC process.

Annex I: Initial TORs given to CLAs at the start of AR6

- Managing content on the Document Management system
- Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions
- Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley
- Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables
- Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)
- Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting
- Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times
- Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and glossary
- Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report
- Assisting with traceability checking
- Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters
- Organisation of chapter teleconferences

Annex II: Copy of survey sent to Chapter Scientists on their role

Introduction

Welcome to the WGI AR6 Chapter Scientists feedback survey!

Thank you very much for providing your feedback to this unique and essential role in drafting the IPCC reports. This survey will be open from 14 to 28 March 2022. It consists of 15 questions and will take approximately 10 minutes to complete. All responses are anonymous, and the data and the analysis will be handled by the WGI TSU. This survey will be used to develop a feedback and lessons learned report to inform the AR7 on the Chapter Scientist role.

Thank you.

Reminder of the task specified in the Chapter Scientist Term of Reference (developed by LAM2)

- Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report
- Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley
- Managing content on the Document Management system
- Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions
- Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables
- Assisting with traceability checking
- Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters
- Technical editing
- Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting.
- Organisation of chapter teleconferences

- Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times
- Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and glossary. At Lead Author Meetings, Chapter Scientists may be asked to assist with other roles, including cross-chapter technical support or meeting logistical support.

1. At what point in the AR6 cycle did you join the WGI team?

By LAM1 (June 2018)

By LAM2 (January 2019)

By LAM3 (August 2019)

By the virtual pre-lam4 (June 2020)

By the virtual LAM4 (January 2021)

I don't remember

2. What type of contract was your chapter scientist role?

Part time whilst studying (e.g., for a PhD or Masters)

Part time whilst researching (e.g. during a post-doc)

Full time contract

Other (please specify)

3. Which tasks did you carry out as part of your Chapter Scientist role? (tick all that apply)

Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report

Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley

Managing content on the Document Management system

Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions

Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables

Assisting with traceability checking

Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters

Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)

Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting.

Organisation of chapter teleconferences

Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating

correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times

Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and

glossary. At Lead Author Meetings, Chapter Scientists may be asked to assist with other roles, including

cross-chapter technical support or meeting logistical support.

4. Did you end up working beyond the stated terms of reference above? Please list the types of work you were additionally involved with.

5. If you were involved with chapter assessment, were you accredited as a contributing author for your chapter?

Yes

No

Any comments:

6. Do you have any suggested edits to the Terms of References? (e.g., any additions or removals)

7. How time-consuming were these tasks with respect to your overall Chapter Scientist role? Please tick 'N/A' if you do not take part in some of these tasks):

Minimal / not time consuming, Somewhat time consuming, Pretty time consuming, Very time consuming, I don't know, N/A

Using the Mendeley software

Managing files on the DMS

Using the Word template

Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)

FOD chapter compilation

SOD chapter compilation

FGD chapter compilation

Updating excel spreadsheets of review comments and responses

Figure development

Uploading the metadata of chapter figures to Figure Manager

Compiling data Tables

Code & data archival

Other (please specify)

8. Do you have any suggestions to improve the efficiency and usability of the topics listed in the previous question?

Using the Mendeley software

Managing files on DMS

Using the Word template

Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)

Chapter compilation

Updating excel spreadsheets of review comments and responses

Figure development

Uploading the metadata of chapter figures to Figure Manager

Compiling data Tables

Code & data archival

9. Were the tools, guidance documents, and training provided by the TSU helpful?

Extremely helpful

Very helpful

Somewhat helpful

Not so helpful

Not at all helpful

I don't know

Not applicable

Do you have any suggestions to improve Chapter scientist support and training?

10. During LAMs and sometimes in between meetings, the TSU would organise Chapter Scientist meetings to allow cross-chapter discussions. How helpful were these meetings to learn and discuss with other chapters?

Very helpful

Somewhat helpful

Neither helpful or unhelpful

Somewhat unhelpful

Very unhelpful

I don't know

Not applicable

How could these cross-chapter Chapter Scientists meetings be improved in the future?

11. What was the best part of being a chapter scientist?

12. What was the worst part of being a chapter scientist?

13. Do you have any suggestions to reduce the negative aspects of the Chapter Scientist role?

14. How likely are you to recommend this role to others in the future?

Very likely

Likely

Neither likely nor unlikely

Unlikely

Very unlikely

I don't know

15. Do you have any more general feedback on the Chapter Scientist role or do you have anything else you'd like to share with us?

Annex III: Copy of survey sent to CLAs on the Chapter Science role

Introduction

Thank you for taking part in this survey sent by the WGI TSU.

Here is a reminder of the initial Chapter Scientists Terms of Reference (ToR) that were provided to chapters towards the start of the AR6 cycle:

- Managing content on the Document Management system
- Assisting the author team in compiling, revising and organising chapter contributions
- Maintaining a complete set of references, checking references in the chapter and reference management with Mendeley
- Assisting in the design and development of figures and tables
- Technical editing (e.g., edits for consistency in your chapter)
- Keeping records of review responses up to date and accurate in formal reporting
- Assisting CLAs during online meetings and at Lead Author Meetings, e.g. note taking, coordinating correspondence between authors, coordinating online meeting times
- Assisting with quality control in relation to the application of the style guide, chapter formatting and glossary
- Identification and compilation of references related to the objectives of the report
- Assisting with traceability checking
- Monitoring overlaps or inconsistencies across chapters
- Organisation of chapter teleconferences

1. In which Chapter were you based?

- Chapter 1
- Chapter 2
- Chapter 3
- Chapter 4
- Chapter 5
- Chapter 6
- Chapter 7
- Chapter 8
- Chapter 9
- Chapter 10
- Chapter 11
- Chapter 12
- Atlas

2. How did you find your Chapter Scientist(s)? Select all that apply.

- I or my co-CLA formally announced/advertised the position
- I or my co-CLA directly appointed a current student/colleague that I or my co-CLA knew or had been working with
- I or my co-CLA directly appointed a former student/colleague that I or my co-CLA knew or had been working with
- Other (please specify)

3. What was the level of commitment of the Chapter Scientist(s)? Select all that apply.

- Role was part-time whilst Chapter Scientist(s) was studying (e.g., for a PhD or Masters)
- Role was part-time whilst Chapter Scientist(s) was working
- Role was full-time
- Other (please specify)

4. How was your Chapter Scientist(s) funded? Select all that apply.

Chapter Scientist(s) was fully covered by existing projects/student grant
Chapter Scientist(s) received top-up on existing projects/student grant
It was a new position that was fully paid
It was a position that had no financial compensation/it was a voluntary position
Other (please specify)

5. What were the main skills you looked for in recruiting a chapter scientist?

6. Were the Terms of Reference (ToR) provided by the TSU for the role of Chapter Scientist helpful and sufficient?

I do not recall receiving the ToR

Yes, the ToR clearly laid out the role and responsibilities of Chapter Scientists

No, information was lacking in the ToR

Any comment:

7. Ideally, how many chapter scientists does a chapter need? How many are needed at a minimum?

8. In your experience, is it better to have chapter scientists: (Select all that apply) work full time or part time?

Work full time

Work part time

Located at a CLA institution

Located at an LA institution

Located anywhere

I don't know

Any comment:

9. Do you think there should be a mechanism or framework established by the IPCC to involve a chapter scientist from a developing country for each report chapter (e.g. to improve geographical balance of those involved in the process, and to grow capacity for early career scientists that could also become future authors)?

Yes

No

I don't know

Please explain your answer and provide any suggestions for how this could be done:

10. Do you have any else you would like to say concerning the Chapter Scientist role?